

An intuitive approach for spike removal in Raman spectra based on peaks' prominence and width

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Two intuitive algorithms are proposed for spike removal in Raman spectra.
- The first algorithm uses thresholds on the widths and prominences of the spectrum's peaks.
- The second one uses the prominence/width ratio for automated detection of spikes.
- The algorithm detects spikes down to 1.1 signal-to-noise ratio.
- The algorithms implementations in Python are available in the author's Github account.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Raman spectroscopists are familiar with the challenge of dealing with spikes caused by cosmic rays. These artifacts may lead to errors in subsequent data processing steps, such as for example calibration, normalization or spectral search. Spike removal is therefore a fundamental step in Raman spectral data pre-treatment, but access to publicly accessible code for spike removal tools is limited, and their performance for spectra correction often unknown. Therefore, there is a need for development and testing open-source and easy-to-implement algorithms that improve the Raman data processing workflow.

Results: In this work, we present and validate two approaches for spike detection and correction in Raman spectral data from graphene: i) An algorithm based on the peaks' widths and prominences and ii) an algorithm based on the ratio of these two peak features. The first algorithm provides an efficient and reliable approach for spike detection in real and synthetic Raman spectra by imposing thresholds on the peaks' width and prominence. The second approach leverages the prominence/width ratio for outlier detection. It relies on the calculation of a limit of detection based on either one or several spectra, enabling the automatic identification of cosmic ray and low-intensity noise-originated spikes alike. Both algorithms detect low-intensity spikes down to at least $\approx 10\%$ of the highest Raman peak of spectra with different noise levels. To address their limitations and prove their versatility, the algorithms were further tested in Raman spectra from calcite and polystyrene.

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Significance: Our intuitive, open-source algorithms have been validated and allow automatic correction for a given set of samples. They do not require any pre-processing steps such as calibration or baseline subtraction, and their implementation with Python libraries is computationally efficient, allowing for immediate utilization within existing open-source packages for Raman spectra processing.

1. Introduction

Spike removal is a fundamental step during the pre-treatment phase of Raman data processing [1,2]. Spikes originate from cosmic rays hitting the detector during the acquisition of a spectrum. Cosmic particles can cause an intense and sharp signal burst at a single pixel position on a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera, the most common detector in Raman spectrometers, that sometimes spreads to a few neighbouring pixels. This results in the generation of electrons that are read out along with the charges induced by the energy of Raman scattered photons, thus giving rise to a corresponding spike in the Raman spectrum [3–5]. These features normally appear as very high-intensity peaks with a very narrow width, and always on a position independent of the spectral wavenumber. If left uncorrected, spikes might lead to errors in subsequent data processing steps such as normalization, calibration, spectral search or dimensionality reduction [1]. The possibility of automatically removing spikes becomes particularly attractive for the automatic processing of vast amounts of Raman spectra, which may foster potential applications of Raman spectroscopy in various industries where large datasets are recorded, whether they are in the form of hyperspectral maps, time series of single measurements as in factory process control, or just massive collections of spectral data. These may include food safety [6] and quality assessment [7], environmental monitoring [8], medical diagnostics [9,10], and bioanalytics in general [11]. In these applications, large datasets are recorded which require an automated analysis. Various methodologies for spike removal have been explored, which can be divided into two classes: single-spectrum and multi-spectrum techniques. Single-spectrum methods operate within individual spectra, employing moving window [12] and polynomial [13] filters, wavelet transform methods [14–16] or Z-scores calculation on the first derivative of the spectrum [17] among others. Conversely, multi-spectrum techniques require the acquisition of several spectra, as in the case of Renishaw's WiRE software which offers the option of taking three spectra to later neglect the outliers pixels among the spectra. More recent multi-spectrum approaches might involve innovative strategies such as convolutional neural networks [18], outlier detection in intensity distributions [19], and 2D Laplacian filtering to enhance spike detection in hyperspectral data [20]. While most single-spectrum methods are based on smoothing or filtering the spectrum, therefore distorting it, multiple-spectra methods typically require either similar or slow varying spectra (so they can be compared between the closest neighbours, be it in time or spatial coordinates), which is not always possible for all applications. In this contribution, we present a single-spectrum spike removal algorithm based on the width and prominence of the peaks found on a spectrum, where corrupted points are corrected by interpolation. While similar approaches might be used on commercial softwares such as Renishaw's WiRE, only the parameters "width" and "height" can be tuned, having no control neither over further required parameters nor over the spectrum correction approach. To the best of our knowledge, no resembling algorithm was implemented in the open-source tools examined during the course of this study either [21–28]. In addition, this study provides an in-depth examination of the functionality and applicability of the presented algorithm, offering valuable insights that can support its integration into the already existing open-source libraries for Raman spectra processing. We demonstrate the efficacy of our approach through two illustrative examples based on graphene Raman spectra. Graphene is a well-known reference material with a strong and well-understood Raman response [29–31], which has already proven to be a useful model system [32]. In

the first example, two 1000 Raman hyperspectral datasets recorded on the same region of the sample are employed. After manual adjustment and verification of the parameters to detect all the spikes on the first dataset, these parameters are successfully applied to the second set, assuring its validation. This shows that once the parameters are appropriately adjusted for a specific type of measurement (same samples, experimental setups, and measuring conditions), they remain effective for subsequent datasets of a similar nature without further tuning. For the second example, we investigate artificial spikes with low intensity to further demonstrate the algorithm's effectiveness under challenging conditions. Additionally, we propose a second method based on the calculation of prominence/width ratios. This approach can be used either as a single- or a multi-spectrum approach to automatically distinguish spikes from genuine Raman bands by applying an outlier detection method to the prominence/width ratios of all peaks found in the spectral dataset. Finally, both algorithms are tested for synthetic spikes in rather challenging narrow-band materials such as polystyrene and calcite.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples and datasets

The sample used to obtain the Raman spectra consists of chemical vapour deposition (CVD) grown graphene transferred onto a glass substrate with lithographically defined gold contacts covering specific regions of the sample. Therefore, different areas render different spectral Raman band intensities and noise, with different Raman band ratios, providing different scenarios to test the spike removal algorithm. Two hyperspectral datasets of the same sample region, one for testing and one for validation, of 1000 spectra each, were recorded with 1 s integration time per spectrum using a Renishaw InVia confocal microscope equipped with a 633 nm laser for excitation and a 1200 lines/mm grating in static mode.

In addition, two other commercial samples with especially narrow bands were tested to define the limitations of the algorithms. Calcite and polystyrene samples were measured with a Renishaw Qontor system, using a 514 nm laser at full power, a 2400 lines/mm grating in static mode, with an integration time of 136 s and 10 s, respectively.

2.2. Computer system

All calculations were carried out using Python (version 3.9.7) running on a Windows 11 Pro 64-Bit system (Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10510U CPU @ 1.80 GHz 2.30 GHz with 16 GB RAM). The used libraries were NumPy [33] (version 1.21.5), Matplotlib [34] (version 3.5.3) and SciPy [35] (version 1.7.3). All Raman data were imported into Jupyter notebooks as a 2-dimensional NumPy array with Raman spectra arranged in the same order as they were measured, where one dimension corresponds to the Raman shift and the other to the spatial coordinates. No prior pre-processing step was applied to the spectra.

2.3. Description of the prominence-fwhm-based algorithm

The spike removal procedure can be divided into four steps: Peak finding, spike detection and flagging, and spectrum correction. Each step is associated with a parameter. Peak finding and spike detection will be based on the values of the prominence and width of the found peaks, respectively. While default values can be guessed for a first test of

the algorithm (threshold width below the expected minimum Raman bandwidth and prominence threshold as a percentage of the most intense peak's prominence or the spectrometer saturation intensity), these two parameters primarily depend on the material under study (width and intensity ratio of its Raman bands), the spectrum noise level and the spectral resolution. Spike flagging and spectrum correction steps rely on the relative height at which the width is evaluated and the number of non-corrupted points, m , used to estimate the interpolation, respectively. The value of these last two parameters might depend on the position of the spike on the spectrum and the local noise. However, within reasonable limits and after testing the same values across various scenarios their influence on the performance appears to be rather minimal.

Peak finding. Finding the peaks in a spectrum can be accomplished by identifying the signal's local maxima. This involves comparing each data point with its neighbours, seeking peaks where the data value surpasses both the left and right neighbours, subjected to a specified prominence value. Here, the prominence parameter serves as a threshold, establishing the minimum vertical difference between a peak and its neighbouring valleys. Peaks that demonstrate a prominence higher than the specified threshold value are recognized as significant, and thereby detected, neglecting less intense peaks originated from background noise fluctuations.

Spike detection. To identify spikes, the detected peaks are further processed by calculating their respective widths. The width is calculated as the full width at half maximum (FWHM), which is determined by finding the points at which the peak prominence drops to half of its maximum value on either side. The difference between these two points can be considered the peak width. By selecting only the peaks with a width below a threshold, spikes can be effectively identified, based on their narrow width characteristics. Note that within this manuscript, as opposed to employing cm^{-1} units, widths are addressed using CCD pixel units. This is due to the fact that spikes relate to pixels of a CCD camera and not to the wavenumber, therefore not being affected by spectral dispersion.

Spike flagging. Once a spike has been located, the corresponding points in the spectrum that are affected by the spike must be identified. To calculate the range where points will be considered corrupted, we can choose the relative height at which the peak width is measured as a percentage of its prominence. In order words, to calculate this range we employ the full width, not at half maximum, but at our own selected height of the spike, between 0 and 1, where 1 corresponds to the width of the peak at its lower contour line, 0.5 evaluates at half the prominence height, and the minimum value is 0. This definition is inherited from the `rel_height` parameter of SciPy's `peak_widths` tool [35]. All points falling within this window are flagged as corrupted, effectively accounting for the impact of the detected cosmic rays in the overall spectral data. For most results presented in this publication, and unless otherwise stated, a value of 0.8 has been used. This value was manually chosen, so even low-intensity corrupted pixels, next to a high-intensity one are flagged. Note that using high values might affect the surroundings of the spike, including nearby Raman bands.

Spectrum correction. The final step in the spike removal process involves replacing the values of the corrupted points with interpolated values. These interpolated values are obtained at each candidate wavenumber by performing a linear, quadratic, or cubic spline interpolation of its immediate neighbours within a window of $2m + 1$ values, where m is a parameter that can be, as the type of interpolation, adjusted by the user. $m = 10$ was used for most results presented in this publication, as this window effectively captures the relevant neighbouring data points surrounding each candidate, for an accurate estimation of interpolated values. As an alternative to interpolation, the corrupted points might be corrected with a simple moving average filter [17]. Deleting was not considered as an option, as this might result in problems during later processing steps [1] if spectra do not have the same amount of points.

This proposed approach was implemented in Python, utilizing SciPy [35] and NumPy [33] libraries for scientific computing. The code can be found in the personal GitHub account of the author.

The algorithm working principle is exemplified in Figs. 1 and 2. Red dots in Fig. 1(a) indicate all peaks found in a spike-contaminated graphene spectrum (light blue line). The Raman spectrum of graphene is mainly composed of the D, G and 2D Raman bands [29]. The G peak corresponds to the high-frequency E_{2g} phonon mode at the Brillouin zone centre (Γ point). The D peak arises from the radial breathing modes of six-atom rings and requires the presence of a defect for its activation [36]. Defects are connected to the lattice symmetry-breaking regions such as sp^3 defects, vacancy sites, as well as edges [37]. The 2D peak arises from a two-phonon double resonance process and is highly sensitive to the number of graphene layers. Besides the spike and the Raman bands, many peaks are identified in the noise. Nevertheless, their prominence is much lower than the prominence of the Raman bands and the spike (see the green circles in Fig. 1(b)). So, a prominence threshold of $P_0 = 20$ counts, for example, could already separate this noise from the real spike and the Raman bands. This fact, in combination with the small width of the spike, and therefore setting a threshold of $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels for example, suffices to locate the spike on the spectrum, discarding noise for having low prominence and the Raman bands for having a wider width (see the width values as blue triangles in Fig. 1(b)). Fig. 2 zooms in on the spike range of Fig. 1. All points within the calculated width at 80 % of the prominence of the peak are considered corrupted, as denoted by the red dashed lines. This allows to identify not only the central and most intense point of the spike but also its tail, in case it is present. For each corrupted pixel, a new value is linearly interpolated based on the $m = 10$ neighbouring points to each side of the

Fig. 1. Width and prominence of all peaks found in a typical graphene spectrum from the dataset. (a) Graphene spectrum where the D band, G band, a spike and the 2D band are present and the grey dashed line notes their position. (b) Width calculated as the $FWHM$ (blue triangles) and $prominence$ (green circles) of the found peaks. (c) $Prominence/FWHM$ ratio showing a clear contrast between noise and Raman bands and the spike. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Zoom in the spike region, showing the raw spectrum in blue, the corrupted area between the two red dashed lines, and the corrected spectrum in orange. The spectrum is corrected by replacing corrupted pixels with linear spline interpolated values. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

pixel, without taking into account other corrupted points. The corrected spectrum is plotted as an orange line. Note that there is also the possibility of two spikes appearing very close together. In that case, the algorithm needs to be implemented in a way that the m chosen points for interpolation do not contain corrupted points from a neighbouring spike.

2.4. Automated spike detection in hyperspectral datasets using peaks' prominence/ $FWHM$ ratios

Leveraging prominence and $FWHM$ of peaks separately offers an intuitive approach, where threshold values can be set based on experience. However, when dealing with large hyperspectral datasets, composed of unknown spectra, an automated approach can prove very handy. To this purpose, we can combine *prominence* and $FWHM$ into a single feature as *prominence/ $FWHM$* , in order to take advantage of the large prominence and narrow width of spikes when compared with Raman bands and noise. The values of *prominence/ $FWHM$* show a large contrast to Raman bands, which are indistinguishable from the background peaks, as shown by the example in Fig. 1(c). Therefore, this feature engineering makes it feasible to detect the spikes by a simple outlier detection approach such as setting a limit of detection (LoD) equal to 3.5 times the standard deviation of the values above their mean value [38]. Any peak with a *prominence/ $FWHM$* value surpassing this threshold will be considered a spike. This method is equivalent to calculating the Z scores of the *prominence/ $FWHM$* values and applying a threshold of $|z_{\text{threshold}}| = 3.5$ for spike identification, a common criterion also proposed by the American Society of Quality Control [17,39].

This spike removal procedure is to be applied to a full hyperspectral dataset together and can also be divided into the four steps mentioned before. First, the peak finding is performed without the need for a prominence threshold, allowing small noise-originating spikes to be included in the study. Spike detection is based on applying a LoD to the *prominence/ $FWHM$* . Finally, Spike flagging and spectra correction are carried out as described before.

As will be shown in the experimental section, this algorithm can be applied as a both single-spectrum and multi-spectrum approach. However, if it is to be used in automation, the reader should note that the calculation of the LoD is required, which relies on having a large number of Raman peaks on a single spectrum, or several spectra from which to obtain a reasonable value.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Parameter exploration and validation with real data

A total of 2000 experimental Raman spectra of graphene were recorded in two datasets of 1000 each, exhibiting various Raman band intensity ratios and noise levels, as well as occasional spikes (see the three examples in Fig. 3). The first dataset was used to manually adjust the parameters in order to detect all the spikes present in the spectra. The second set of 1000 spectra was then used to validate these parameters. Fig. 4(a) displays the first set of 1000 Raman spectra. The spectra are plotted with alternating colours to help visualization. After adjusting the initial parameters ($P_0 = 40$ counts, $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels), the algorithm identified and corrected 39 spikes through linear spline interpolation of neighbouring values. These spikes were found to be the only ones present in the 1000 spectra by visual inspection of the full dataset. See the corrected spectra in Fig. 4(b) where the graphene bands can now be easily observed. Different types of spikes were detected and corrected. As examples, Fig. 5 displays a 1-pixel spike (a), a 4-pixel spike (b) and a set of two consecutive spikes of different intensity and width, the first laying on the shoulder of the G band (c), respectively.

While linear spline interpolation suffices to fix most corrupted spectra, some more challenging scenarios are also possible. For example, Fig. 6 shows the case of a spike on top of the 2D Raman band of graphene. Using the same parameters as before (width at 80 % of the peak height) and a linear spline results in a truncated Raman band (see Fig. 6 (a)). One possibility to sort out this situation could be to reduce the corrupted area from widths at 80 % of the prominence to widths at 30 % (Fig. 6(c)). Alternatively, the use of a quadratic spline would result in a more accurate representation of the peak for both windows (Fig. 6 (b-d)). One should note, however, that using a quadratic spline on more simple cases might introduce artifacts.

Once the spikes are separated and clean spectra are obtained by interpolation, one can cross-check the used parameters and address whether they will be useful for further analysis of new datasets. The prominence and $FWHM$ of all peaks found by the peak finding algorithm are presented as grey dots in the scatter plot in Fig. 7. The detected spikes are coloured in red. For the sake of having a reference, the points corresponding to the D, G and 2D bands are coloured in green, orange and blue, respectively. The peaks corresponding to such bands were searched for within a 21-pixel window around their main observed Raman shift position, with an $FWHM$ threshold of $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels and no threshold in prominence. The 21-pixel window allows for detecting the peak even if spectral noise shifted the peak maxima. Two clearly separated groups of peaks can be observed. On one side we have the points corresponding to noise and Raman bands. The points belonging to the 2D band could be grouped into two sets of different prominence. This is probably due to the fact that graphene lies either on glass or on gold,

Fig. 3. Three example spectra of graphene on glass showing different Raman band ratios, backgrounds and noise levels.

Fig. 4. Despiking example with graphene Raman spectra. (a) A test dataset consisting of 1000 spectra where some of them exhibit spikes. (b) The same 1000 spectra after spike removal with parameters $P_0 = 40$ counts and $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels. The spectra are plotted with alternating colours to help visualization. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Examples of types of spikes removed by the algorithm in case study 1: (a) 1-pixel, (b) 4-pixel and (c) two consecutive several-pixel spikes. The blue dotted line corresponds to the raw spectra, while the orange spectra correspond to the corrected spectra. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

leading to distributions of intensity around two main values corresponding to glass (higher prominence) and gold (lower prominence), as exemplified in Fig. 3. The points corresponding to the D and G bands are also visible, presenting lower prominence but a broader range of FWHM values, the D band being the broadest. Different widths and intensity ratios between bands are expected, due to defects, doping or strain [40, 41]. Peaks originating from noise are present with a large dispersion in FWHM, but are all below the imposed threshold in prominence of $P_0 = 40$ counts. On the other side, we have the points corresponding to the detected spikes, in red colour, which are efficiently boxed by the chosen thresholds, most of them well above the prominence of the majority of all peaks. Note that for visualization purposes the y-axis of the plot has been limited from 0 to 400 counts, while the most intense spike has a prominence of 1065 counts and the prominence distribution presents a median of 334 counts. Mean and standard deviation values of

Fig. 6. A spike detected on top of the Raman 2D band is corrected with linear (first column) and quadratic (second column) splines and width at either the 80% (first row) or the 30% (second row) of the peak height. Parameters used: $P_0 = 50$ counts and $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels.

Fig. 7. Scatter plot of FWHM and prominence values of all peaks found in the 1000 spectra shown in Fig. 4 (grey dots). The peaks corresponding to spikes, the D band, the G band and the 2D band are coloured in red, green, orange and blue, respectively. The horizontal black dashed line corresponds to the prominence threshold of $P_0 = 40$ counts and the vertical one to the FWHM threshold of $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 1

Mean and standard deviation of the prominence and FWHM of the main graphene Raman bands and the detected spikes.

Band	Prominence	FWHM (pixels)	FWHM (cm^{-1})
D	54 ± 14	25 ± 8	64 ± 21
G	67 ± 23	16 ± 10	40 ± 26
2D	132 ± 68	18 ± 2	45 ± 6
All peaks	8 ± 10	2 ± 2	–
Spikes	439 ± 294	1.5 ± 0.6	–

prominence and FWHM of the different bands and peaks can be seen in Table 1. From this, we can contrast that our chosen parameters not only worked well but they also detected three low-intensity spikes (see the three red dots slightly above the prominence threshold in the figure). In summary, this two-dimensional representation leads us to the conclusion, that in general, thresholds in prominence and FWHM can be selected with flexibility as there is a clear separation between spikes and real Raman bands.

In order to cross-check the selected thresholds for peak search (prominence) and spike identification (FWHM), we applied the algorithm to a validation set of data composed of 1000 additional raw Raman spectra (Fig. 8(a)). In this case, 23 corrupted spectra were found and corrected with the same parameters as for the test set (Fig. 8(b)). The validation with an independent dataset demonstrates the efficacy of the proposed algorithm with the selected parameters for this type of sample, setup and experimental conditions. Consequently, the suggested approach of systematically exploring and selecting parameters specific to a particular measurement type (same setup, acquisition parameters and sample), and subsequently applying them to other datasets obtained using the same measurement type, proved to be fully effective. Furthermore, the algorithm exhibits remarkable efficiency, completing the processing of 1000 spectra in less than ~ 0.5 s. This rapid processing time makes it a very suitable choice for its implementation in automated in-line analysis.

3.2. Automatic detection of spikes in real hyperspectral data

The fact that two clearly separated clusters can be observed in Fig. 7 opens the path to the use of clustering algorithms (e.g. k-means [42], DBSCAN [43], etc.) for the automatic selection of thresholds. However, an even simpler approach consists of combining *prominence* and *FWHM* into a single feature as *prominence/FWHM*, as described in section 2.4, taking advantage of the large prominence and narrow width of spikes when compared with Raman bands and noise. The frequency histogram of the values of this new parameter for the test dataset presented above can be seen in Fig. 9(a). The spikes found with the manually adjusted

Fig. 8. Parameters manually adjusted for the test dataset are successfully used in a validation dataset. (a) A validation dataset consisting of 1000 spectra where some of them show random spikes. (b) The same 1000 spectra after spike removal with the parameters chosen for the test set ($P_0 = 40$ counts and $FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels). The spectra are plotted with alternating colours to help visualization. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Automatic detection of spikes by finding the outliers in the peak's *prominence/FWHM* values of the test dataset. (a) Frequency histogram of the *prominence/FWHM* ratios. The inset zooms in around the black dashed line locating the LoD equal to 3.5 times the standard deviation of the *prominence/FWHM* values above their mean value. (b) Example of three corrupted spectra by spikes with *prominence/FWHM* values of 27, 25 and 23, from top to bottom. The corrected spectra are shown in orange, the identified spikes are marked in blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

parameter method discussed in the previous section are plotted in red, outlying the rest of the data. While the D, G and 2D bands (green, orange and blue bars, respectively) show a very low *prominence/FWHM* value, the peaks originating from noise (grey bars) show a larger dispersion, due to their very narrow FWHM. In the case of our test dataset, the LoD is calculated to be at *prominence/FWHM* = 22 counts/pixel and is plotted as a black dashed line in Fig. 9(a). It effectively separates all found peaks corresponding to Raman bands from the spikes previously detected, therefore demonstrating that this approach is very successful for automatized detection of spikes. In fact, around 100 peaks, which were not detected as spikes by the manual adjustment method, are now identified as spikes. Visual inspection of the identified spectra reveals that the spikes therein exhibit low intensity and are likely not of cosmic origin but rather generated by random noise (see three examples in Fig. 9(b)). Correction of the spectra was carried out by interpolation as explained above and three examples of spectra with low-intensity noise-originating spikes are shown in Fig. 9(b). The corrected spectra are plotted in orange, while the spikes can be observed in blue, proving the enhanced sensitivity of this method. From top to bottom, the identified spikes show a SNR (percentage intensity of the 2D band) of 4.0 (34 %), 4.1 (27 %), and 3.9 (12 %), respectively, where the SNR is calculated as I/I_0 with I as the intensity of each spike and I_0 being the noise level, calculated as the standard deviation of the intensity difference along the Raman shift axis of the spectrum ($dI[i] = I[i + 1] - I[i]$, i stands for the pixel index and $I[i]$ for the intensity value at i). In the case of the test dataset, ~ 0.3 s were required to calculate the threshold and ~ 0.7 s to remove the spikes. This approach not only demonstrates its effectiveness

in automatic spike detection but also opens up the door for further exploration. On one hand, it leaves room for experimentation with other different features, such as p/w^2 , p^2/w , etc. which might perform better depending on the dataset. On the other hand, alternative outlier detection methods beyond the one employed in this study may reveal untapped potential for enhancing spike detection precision and expanding the scope of applications in Raman spectroscopy analysis.

3.3. Detection of low-intensity spikes

As we have seen in the previous subsection, spikes are usually more intense than any Raman band. This makes it relatively straightforward to detect them. Unfortunately, low-intensity spikes that can easily be overlooked by detection algorithms are also sometimes present and may lead to erroneous spectra interpretations. For that reason, the performance of the algorithm was specifically tested for such a possibility. Fig. 10 (a) shows a spectrum where artificial spikes were introduced with relative intensity to the highest Raman band (light blue spectrum). Their intensity ranges from 100 % to 10 % of the highest Raman band. This corresponds to signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) ranging from 11.1 to 1.1, respectively. The red dots indicate the peaks found by the algorithm with FWHM threshold $FWHM_0 = 5$ pixels and prominence threshold $P_0 = 25$ counts, and the corrected spectrum is plotted in orange. Fig. 10 (b) presents the FWHM (blue triangles) and prominence (green circles) of the found peaks, showing that the parameters obtained from the previous case study ($FWHM_0 = 4$ pixels, $P_0 = 40$ counts) provide a spike detection limit of about 50 % intensity of the highest peak (SNR = 5.6). These results are similar to the ones presented in Ref. [20] for

Fig. 10. Removal of low-intensity spikes. (a) Corrected (orange line) and original (blue line) spectra with artificial spikes. The red dots denote the peaks detected by the algorithm. (b) FWHM (blue triangles) and prominence (green circles) of the detected peaks. A threshold of 5 and 25 for FWHM and prominence, respectively, allow for the detection of all spikes. (c) Prominence/ $FWHM$ values of the detected peaks. A threshold of $prominence/FWHM_0 = 6$ allows for the detection of all spikes. The dashed lines indicate the position of the D, G and 2D graphene bands for reference. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

non-consequence datasets, where the authors calculated the detection limit in db with formula $10 \cdot \log_{10}(I/I_0)$, according to which we obtained 17 db. Nonetheless, when using higher width (up to $FWHM_0 = 5$ pixels) and lower prominence (down to $P_0 = 25$ counts) thresholds, the detection limit is reduced to 10 % intensity of the highest peak, corresponding to 1.1 dB (and SNR = 1.1). This indicates that even spikes that are only slightly more intense than the noise can be identified. A similar situation occurs when testing the $Prominence/FWHM$ ratio approach: Using the threshold calculated from the large dataset in the previous section ($Prominence/FWHM_0 = 22$ counts/pixel) results in a detection limit of the 20 % intensity of the highest peak (SNR = 2.2). One can still tune this threshold to the minimum of $Prominence/FWHM_0 = 6$ counts/pixel, allowing for the detection of the minimum intensity spike (10 % intensity of the highest peak, SNR = 1.1). While these algorithms are very powerful in terms of sensitivity, the challenge might lie in their use for automatization of data pre-processing, as large datasets composed of dissimilar spectra with varied noise levels might require high prominence or lower width thresholds, preventing the detection of lower SNR spikes.

3.4. Example of application in materials with narrower bands: calcite and polystyrene

To demonstrate the versatility of the approaches, the algorithms were tested in two other materials. Polystyrene and calcite were chosen as they present very narrow Raman peaks, posing a challenge to the implemented algorithms. In particular, calcite is used for spectral resolution assessment [44]. Besides, both calcite and polystyrene are certified standard reference materials, well-known in the Raman spectroscopy community which can be used for calibration purposes [45]. The first row of Fig. 11 presents a spectrum of calcite, a zoom-in on a spectrum of calcite, and a spectrum of polystyrene. Synthetic spikes were introduced with different intensities and FWHMs. The contaminated spectra (plotted in blue) were corrected with the prominence-FWHM-based approach (plotted in orange), leaving the corrected spikes in blue. The second (third) row of Fig. 11 presents the calculated FWHM and prominence ($prominence/FWHM$ ratio) values. Blue and magenta dashed lines indicate the threshold in $FWHM$ and $prominence/FWHM$, respectively, below and above which values are considered spikes. For the recorded spectra, the observed minimum thresholds were $FWHM_0 = 2.3$ and $prominence/FWHM_0 = 40880$ for calcite and $FWHM_0 = 4$ and $prominence/FWHM_0 = 1700$ for polystyrene. In Fig. 11 (first column), four synthetic spikes with relative intensity to the highest Raman band (25 %, 50 %, 75 % and 100 %) were detected with the prominence-FWHM-based approach. Only the least intense escaped from detection with the $prominence/FWHM$ ratio-based approach. In Fig. 11 (second column) eight synthetic low-intensity spikes were introduced. Four of them with $FWHM = 1$ and relative intensity of 100 %, 75 %, 50 %, 25 % and 12 % to the narrowest Raman band (which correspond to a relative intensity of 0.4 %, 0.32 %, 0.25 %, 0.16 %, 0.08 %, 0.04 % of the highest band of calcite, respectively), and three of them with relative intensity of 75 % and $FWHM = 1.5, 2$ and 3 , respectively. While only the wider spike was not detected by the prominence-FWHM-based approach, neither of them was detected by the $prominence/FWHM$ ratio-based approach, for being extremely small in comparison with the long time-integration spectrum. In Fig. 11 (third column) eight synthetic low-intensity spikes were introduced. Four of them with $FWHM = 1$ and relative intensity to the highest Raman band (40 %, 30 %, 20 % and 10 %), and five of them with a relative intensity of 100 % and $FWHM = 1, 1.5, 2, 2.75$ and 3 , respectively. All of them were detected by the prominence-FWHM-based approach. Only the shortest and the widest ones were not detected by the $prominence/FWHM$ ratio-based approach.

Narrow-band Raman spectra from calcite and polystyrene in combination with artificially small spikes therefore helps to define the

Fig. 11. Synthetic spikes in narrow-Raman-band materials. The first row shows the spectra before and after correction with the prominence-FWHM-based approach. The second row shows the FWHM and Prominence of the found peaks. The third row shows the prominence/FWHM ratio of the found peaks. Blue and magenta dashed lines show the threshold in FWHM and prominence/FWHM respectively. (a) Calcite spectrum with four intensity-increasing artificially added spikes. (b) Zoom-in on a calcite spectrum with artificial spikes with different intensities and widths. (c) Zoom-in on a polystyrene spectrum with artificial spikes with different intensities and widths. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

limitations of the proposed algorithms while showing their suitability even under very challenging scenarios.

4. Conclusions

Two algorithms were introduced in this study for the detection and replacement of spikes within Raman spectral data. Both algorithms were tested against a real dataset, combining low- and high-intensity Raman signals with diverse noise levels and Raman band ratios. The first algorithm, designed for single-spectrum analysis, distinguishes spikes from noise and Raman bands by imposing thresholds to the FWHMs and prominences of the found peaks. After manual parameter adjustment on the test dataset, these thresholds were validated on the second dataset, successfully detecting all visible spikes. The detection limit of this algorithm was estimated to be around 10 % of the highest Raman band intensity or a peak signal-to-noise ratio of 1.1 for the case of graphene spectra. For the case of calcite and polystyrene spectra, it was estimated to be below 50 % and 10 % of the highest Raman band intensities, respectively. While fine-tuning may be necessary for new scenarios, once parameters are adjusted for a specific measurement type, the algorithm can operate autonomously, making it suitable for integration into fully automated processing real-time routines of large hyperspectral mapping measurements and in-line analysis. The second algorithm, tailored for multi-spectrum analysis, automates the spike detection process in hyperspectral datasets by utilizing the *prominence/FWHM* ratio as a discriminative parameter, detecting both regular and low-intensity spikes. Moreover, both implementations can be applied to individual spectra and do not require any pre-treatment step such as calibration or baseline subtraction. These algorithms only correct the spike-corrupted points instead of modifying the full spectrum as would be the case of other approaches such as moving average or Savitzky-Golay filters. Additionally, they are reasonably computationally efficient and can be straightforwardly implemented with open-source libraries, which makes them useable for already working open-source Python packages for Raman spectra processing. The presented results highlight the robustness and reliability of the proposed methods to perform well under diverse conditions, showcasing their practicality and versatility in real-world in-line Raman and hyperspectral data.

Code and data availability

Code and data will be soon available at the GitHub repository of the author (<https://github.com/nicocopez/pyspikes>).

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Nicolas Coca-Lopez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares no competing financial interest.

Data availability

Code and data will be soon available at the GitHub repository of the author (<https://github.com/nicocopez/pyspikes>).

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References

- [1] B. Barton, J. Thomson, E. Lozano Diz, R. Portela, *Chemometrics for Raman spectroscopy harmonization*, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 76 (9) (2022) 1021–1041.
- [2] O. Ryabchykov, S. Guo, T. Bocklitz, *Analyzing Raman spectroscopic data*, *Physical Sciences Reviews* 4 (2) (2018) 20170043.
- [3] G.E. Healey, R. Kondepudy, *Radiometric ccd camera calibration and noise estimation*, *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 16 (3) (1994) 267–276.
- [4] Y.S. Han, E. Choi, M.G. Kang, *Smear removal algorithm using the optical black region for ccd imaging sensors*, *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.* 55 (4) (2009) 2287–2293.
- [5] C.-W. Chow, C.-Y. Chen, S.-H. Chen, *Enhancement of signal performance in led visible light communications using mobile phone camera*, *IEEE Photon. J.* 7 (5) (2015) 1–7.
- [6] M. Petersen, Z. Yu, X. Lu, *Application of Raman spectroscopic methods in food safety: a review*, *Biosensors* 11 (6) (2021) 187.

- [7] T.A. Lintvedt, P.V. Andersen, N.K. Afseth, B. Marquardt, L. Gidskehaug, J.P. Wold, Feasibility of in-line Raman spectroscopy for quality assessment in food industry: how fast can we go? *Appl. Spectrosc.* 76 (5) (2022) 559–568.
- [8] T.T. Ong, E.W. Blanch, O.A. Jones, Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy in environmental analysis, monitoring and assessment, *Sci. Total Environ.* 720 (2020) 137601.
- [9] S. Abbasi, M. Feizpour, I. Weets, Q. Liu, H. Thienpont, F. Ferranti, H. Ottevaere, Classification of hemoglobin fractions in the liquid state using Raman spectroscopy combined with machine learning, *Microchem. J.* 194 (2023) 109305.
- [10] N. Pazos-Perez, E. Pazos, C. Catala, B. Mir-Simon, S. Gómez-de Pedro, J. Sagales, C. Villanueva, J. Vila, A. Soriano, F.J. García de Abajo, et al., Ultrasensitive multiplex optical quantification of bacteria in large samples of biofluids, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (1) (2016) 29014.
- [11] D. Ciolla-May, C. Krafft, P. Rössch, T. Deckert-Gaudig, T. Frosch, L.J. Jahn, S. Pahlow, C. Stiebing, T. Meyer-Zedler, T. Bocklitz, et al., Raman spectroscopy and imaging in bioanalytics, *Anal. Chem.* 94 (1) (2021) 86–119.
- [12] Y. Katsumoto, Y. Ozaki, Practical algorithm for reducing convex spike noises on a spectrum, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 57 (3) (2003) 317–322.
- [13] G. Phillips, J.M. Harris, Polynomial filters for data sets with outlying or missing observations: application to charge-coupled-device-detected Raman spectra contaminated by cosmic rays, *Anal. Chem.* 62 (21) (1990) 2351–2357.
- [14] F. Ehrentreich, L. Sümmchen, Spike removal and denoising of Raman spectra by wavelet transform methods, *Anal. Chem.* 73 (17) (2001) 4364–4373.
- [15] D. Chen, Z. Chen, E. Grant, Adaptive wavelet transform suppresses background and noise for quantitative analysis by Raman spectrometry, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 400 (2011) 625–634.
- [16] A. Maury, R.I. Revilla, Autocorrelation analysis combined with a wavelet transform method to detect and remove cosmic rays in a single Raman spectrum, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 69 (8) (2015) 984–992.
- [17] D.A. Whitaker, K. Hayes, A simple algorithm for despiking Raman spectra, *Chemometr. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 179 (2018) 82–84.
- [18] J. Wahl, M. Sjö Dahl, K. Ramser, Single-step preprocessing of Raman spectra using convolutional neural networks, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 74 (4) (2020) 427–438.
- [19] K. Uckert, R. Bhartia, J. Michel, A semi-autonomous method to detect cosmic rays in Raman hyperspectral data sets, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 73 (9) (2019) 1019–1027.
- [20] O. Ryabchykov, T. Bocklitz, A. Ramoji, U. Neugebauer, M. Foerster, C. Kroegel, M. Bauer, M. Kiehntopf, J. Popp, Automatization of spike correction in Raman spectra of biological samples, *Chemometr. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 155 (2016) 1–6.
- [21] G. Georgiev, L. Iliev, N. Jeliakova, D. Lellinger, ramachada2, Dic 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10255258>. URL, <https://zenodo.org/records/10255258>.
- [22] D. Georgiev, S.V. Pedersen, R. Xie, A. Fernández-Galiana, M.M. Stevens, M. Barahona, Ramanspy: an Open-Source Python Package for Integrative Raman Spectroscopy Data Analysis, 2023 arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.13650.
- [23] A. Travert, C. Fernandez, Spectrochempy, a framework for processing, analyzing and modeling spectroscopic data for chemistry with Python (8 2023). doi:10.5281/zenodo.3823841. URL <https://www.spectrochempy.fr>.
- [24] D. Storozhuk, O. Ryabchykov, J. Popp, T. Bocklitz, Ramanmetrix: a Delightful Way to Analyze Raman Spectra, 2022 arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.07586.
- [25] G. Sheehy, F. Picot, F. Dallaire, K.J. Ember, T. Nguyen, K. Petrecca, D. Trudel, F. Leblond, Open-sourced Raman spectroscopy data processing package implementing a baseline removal algorithm validated from multiple datasets acquired in human tissue and biofluids, *J. Biomed. Opt.* 28 (2) (2023) 025002, <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JBO.28.2.025002>, [10.1117/1.JBO.28.2.025002](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JBO.28.2.025002).
- [26] R.W. Schmidt, S. Woutersen, F. Ariese, Ramanlight—a graphical user-friendly tool for pre-processing and unmixing hyperspectral Raman spectroscopy images, *J. Opt.* 24 (6) (2022) 064011.
- [27] A. Lebrun, BoxSERS, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5557906>. URL, <https://github.com/ALebrun-108/BoxSERS>.
- [28] S. Somnath, C.R. Smith, N. Laanait, R.K. Vasudevan, A. Ievlev, A. Belianinov, A. R. Lupini, M. Shankar, S.V. Kalinin, S. Jesse, USID and Pycroscopy – Open Frameworks for Storing and Analyzing Spectroscopic and Imaging Data, 2019 arXiv:1903.09515.
- [29] H. Budde, N. Coca-López, X. Shi, R. Ciesielski, A. Lombardo, D. Yoon, A.C. Ferrari, A. Hartschuh, Raman radiation patterns of graphene, *ACS Nano* 10 (2) (2016) 1756–1763.
- [30] P. Turner, K.R. Paton, E.J. Legge, A. de Luna Bugallo, A. Rocha-Robledo, A.-A. Zahab, A. Centeno, A. Sacco, A. Pesquera, A. Zurutuza, et al., International interlaboratory comparison of Raman spectroscopic analysis of cvd-grown graphene, *2D Mater.* 9 (3) (2022) 035010.
- [31] A.C. Ferrari, D.M. Basko, Raman spectroscopy as a versatile tool for studying the properties of graphene, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 8 (4) (2013) 235–246.
- [32] N. Coca-López, N.F. Hartmann, T. Mancabelli, J. Kraus, S. Günther, A. Comin, A. Hartschuh, Remote excitation and detection of surface-enhanced Raman scattering from graphene, *Nanoscale* 10 (22) (2018) 10498–10504.
- [33] C.R. Harris, K.J. Millman, S.J. Van Der Walt, R. Gommers, P. Virtanen, D. Cournapeau, E. Wieser, J. Taylor, S. Berg, N.J. Smith, et al., Array programming with numpy, *Nature* 585 (7825) (2020) 357–362.
- [34] J.D. Hunter, Matplotlib: a 2d graphics environment, *Comput. Sci. Eng.* 9 (3) (2007) 90–95.
- [35] P. Virtanen, R. Gommers, T.E. Oliphant, M. Haberland, T. Reddy, D. Cournapeau, E. Burovski, P. Peterson, W. Weckesser, J. Bright, et al., Scipy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python, *Nat. Methods* 17 (3) (2020) 261–272.
- [36] F. Tuinstra, J.L. Koenig, Raman spectrum of graphite, *J. Chem. Phys.* 53 (3) (1970) 1126–1130.
- [37] C. Casiraghi, A. Hartschuh, H. Qian, S. Piscanec, C. Georgi, A. Fasoli, K. Novoselov, D. Basko, A. Ferrari, Raman spectroscopy of graphene edges, *Nano Lett.* 9 (4) (2009) 1433–1441.
- [38] L.A. Currie, Detection and quantification limits: origins and historical overview, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 391 (2) (1999) 127–134.
- [39] B. Iglewicz, D.C. Hoaglin, How to Detect and Handle Outliers, vol. 16, Quality Press, 1993.
- [40] R. Beams, L.G. Cançado, L. Novotny, Raman characterization of defects and dopants in graphene, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 27 (8) (2015) 083002.
- [41] R. Beams, L.G. Cançado, A. Jorio, A.N. Vamivakas, L. Novotny, Tip-enhanced Raman mapping of local strain in graphene, *Nanotechnology* 26 (17) (2015) 175702.
- [42] J.A. Hartigan, M.A. Wong, Algorithm as 136: a k-means clustering algorithm, *Journal of the royal statistical society. series c (applied statistics)* 28 (1) (1979) 100–108.
- [43] M. Ester, H.-P. Kriegel, J. Sander, X. Xu, et al., A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large spatial databases with noise, *kdd 96* (1996) 226–231.
- [44] A. International, Astm e2529–06 Standard guide for testing the resolution of a Raman spectrometer, 2014.
- [45] A. Ntziouni, J. Thomson, I. Xiarchos, X. Li, M.A. Bañares, C. Charitidis, R. Portela, E.L. Diz, Review of existing standards, guides, and practices for Raman spectroscopy, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 76 (7) (2022) 747–772.